

ANALYSIS OF E-FINGERPRINT AUTHENTICATION IN MODERN BIOMETRIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

One of the major problems with the authentication of users via the internet is the inherent lack of security of traditional authentication techniques, passwords PIN numbers and cookies. With the current development of the biometric fingerprint technology market, the possibility of identifying someone online has been addressed. This system is one of the solutions to come out of recent developments. The fingerprint authentication system allows for a web page to include a validation check using objects embedded in the web page which call on an interface to a fingerprint reader attached to the client computer which returns a coded fingerprint to the server where it is then validated.

The biometrics technology grows fast. The BioAPI specification has defined an open system standard application program interface (API) which allows software applications to communicate with a broad range of biometric technologies. BioAPI valuable feature to support fingerprint Authentication. It will provide a new security for users. There exist many laptops that contain an integrated fingerprint reader/sensor, such as Toshiba M5, Lenovo IBM t61/z61, etc. Most of the fingerprint readers use USB as the I/o interface. This project is to make the new security solution available if the laptops and desktops connect to a USB fingerprint reader.

Fingerprint identification involves comparing the pattern of ridges and furrows on the fingertips, as well as the minutiae points (ridge characteristics that occur when a ridge splits into two, or ends) of a specimen print with a database of prints on file.

Keywords: Fingerprint, PIN, BioAPI, CAS

Introduction

Fingerprint Authentication for web applications is a web-based technology for authenticating users before entering into their respective web applications through their unique biometrics like fingerprints, iris, voice etc. This technology is highly secure and reliable than many other technologies used in common like password verification etc as it verifies with the human being's unique identity features which are mentioned above.

The whole aim of this software technique is to provide safe, reliable and secured way of transactions among web users as security threats and fraudulent data transformations are common in our day to day life. This software is one of the steps to answer the problem of hacking and other information thefts.

This software uses fingerprint scanning which is one of the biometric technologies for authentication users. Users fingerprint is being scanned and it is stored in a database server along with other details of the user as in normal authentication. The stored fingerprint is being verified at the time of signing in into the web application and then the

user is authenticated. As the scanned fingerprint uses encryption and decryption techniques so there is no chance of pit-falls like hacking the fingerprints etc.

Definition

Any biometric recognition procedure can be divided into a number of stages.

1. Acquisition of a biometric sample (device-dependent processing)
2. Extraction of a biometric template (user-template creation)
3. Biometric template matching (pattern recognition processing).

In this application the following things is being done to check whether a user is a valid person:

- Creating an account for a new user after getting user profiles.
- Creating a unique user name.
- Receiving a fingerprint from the user and storing it in server
- Authenticating the user using the fingerprint

For administrator they are the users who use the system with all privileges and give control to the other users of the system. But the number of hits by these users is much less compared to others. The users have certain privilege to update the personal details of the users and also to access databases to change values present.

For the users are the prime users of the system for whom the whole system and all intended functionalities are created. These users use the system more often than the other users i.e. the frequency of usage is high in this case.

All the functionalities of the system are to be accessible by these users and the functionalities and documentations should be intended to be understood and grasped easily by them.

For Example:

Creating an account for a new user after getting user profiles:

This process creates a new account for a user after getting the user's details like first name, last name, age, date of birth etc.

After getting user profiles then a unique user name has to be created for further communications and verifications. Receiving a fingerprint from the user and storing it in server. The next step of the software is to get the finger print of the software that is unique in nature from all others using a fingerprint scanner and must store it in the database server.

Authentication the user:

Authenticating user after matching user name and fingerprint that are stored in server database

Users enroll their fingerprint once on the system. The fingerprint template resides on the network server.

Users can authenticate using their fingerprints on any PC connected to the network server; bases on policies set by the network administrator.

For example, if the network server is unavailable, a user could still logon at their desktop using their fingerprint.

In a normal method of web authentication and other authentication techniques user-names and passwords are being used and they are matched for the validity of the user. Though passwords are reliable but there is a possibility of hacking the passwords while the user is authenticating him in different places by the intruders and hackers, even though the user kept a 10 characters or higher as password, also in another possibility neighbors could identify it while typing, in some other times even people after typing the user name without seeing the screen would type password in user name column which exposes to others. So this password protection is no longer a fool proof method in web and other internet applications for safe use.

Fingerprint biometrics are a leading digital technology that can be utilized in digital identity authentication. Those in a point of service setting that use fingerprint biometrics do so by scanning a user's ID through a system and instructing the user to use a keypad to match fingerprints with a stored fingerprint identity. Fingerprint biometrics help increase the chances that the person in front of you presenting an ID is that ID's true identity. The result is an ability to capture and link fingerprints to a single ID record, which will increase fraud prevention and help ensure fraudsters do not attempt to use multiple identities, which uses a biometric method for authentication is a completely different method for authentication. It uses a finger print template as an authentication tool. The template is sent to the server after encryption so it is a very safe and secure technique. So this method is secure as well as fool proof for any secured transactions of data and other confidential things. Anyone can see our fingerprints but no in this world can make a fingerprint like that or can have a fingerprint like ours.

Those in a point of service setting pay for fraud twice, once stemming from the initial act of fraud and a second time as a result of cost of goods, services and even insurance rates increases. Biometric verification can help resolve the problem of ID fraud and provide the point of service person that the user presented is the actual person represented on the

ID. The benefit of a biometric verification is that legitimate multiple IDs can be linked to a single person through one unique biometric fingerprint records. The additional benefit is that this unique biometric fingerprint can not be utilized in multiple fraudulent IDs.

Fingerprint identification (referred to as *dactyloscopy*) is the process of comparing questioned and known friction skin ridge impressions from fingers, palms, and toes to determine if the impressions are from the same finger (or palm, toe, etc.). The flexibility of friction ridge skin means that no two finger or palm prints are ever exactly alike (never identical in every detail), even two impressions recorded immediately after each other.

Fingerprint identification (also referred to as individualization) occurs when an expert (or an expert computer system operating under threshold scoring rules) determines that two friction ridge impressions originated from the same finger or palm (or toe, sole) to the exclusion of all others.

In the software and device, about Nitgen device

Fingerprint Recognition Hamster is a fingerprint scanner for a computer Security featuring superior performance, accuracy, durability based on unique NITGEN Fingerprint Biometric Technology. It can be plugged into a computer separately with your mouse. It is very safe and convenient device for security instead of password that is vulnerable to fraud and is hard to remember. Use Hamster with your choice of compatible biometric software for authentication, identification and verification functions that let your fingerprints act like digital passwords that cannot be lost, forgotten or stolen.

Applications

- Personal computer / workstation security.
- Network / enterprise security.
- E-commerce / e-business.
- Electronic transactions.

Conclusion

In future we have successfully integrated biometric verification functionality within a widely accepted open source solution for single sign-on web authentication called Central Authentication Service (CAS). Thus, any application prepared to use CAS for authenticating its users can also use our biometric extension for this purpose. The overall system provides single sign-on web authentication beyond basic mechanisms based on

login and password, by adding biometrics. Concretely, the future biometric extension of CAS supports any BioAPI-compliant biometric software or devices in order to authenticate users. As a result, any BioAPI-compliant kind of biometric verification could be used in order to get single-sign-on web authentication.

In order to demonstrate the usability of biometric extension of CAS, we can tested successfully the overall system with different web applications that allows the use of CAS to authenticate users, such as the open-source e-learning platforms Model are using regarding future lines of work, the experts are analyzing the viability of porting the biometric system for web authentication to mobile devices.

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